

F·A·A·M facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B122
 Date: 17 Aug 2005
 Take Off 08:02:23 14:58:58
 Landing: 13:18:40 16:08:07
 Flight Time 5h16m17 1h09m09

Campaign: CLOPAP

Operating Area: N Sea, Scotland

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Alan Roberts	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist	Keith Bower	Manchester University
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics	Martin Pickering	Met Office
7	CVI/CCN	Paul James	FAAM
8	PTRMS	Jennifer Murphy	UEA
9	CPI	Martin Gallagher	Manchester University
10	AMS	Gerard Capes	Manchester University
11	Core Chem / CCM2	Ruth Purvis	FAAM
12	NOxy	Dave Stewart	UEA
13	WAS	Maria Nielsdottir	UEA
14			
15			
16			
17			
18			
19			
20			

Flight Track:

B122 Track 17-AUG-05

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b122
 Date: 17/8/05
 Project: Cirrus
 Location: N Sea, Scotland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
075022		inu to nav	0.14 kft	126	
075543		taxy start	0.14 kft	126	
080223		T/O	0.13 kft	032	from cranfield
080540		jw/nevz zero	5.2 kft	300	
080616		asp open	6.3 kft	289	
090140	092428	Profile 1	18.0 - 30.0 kft	090	start FL180
090621		Profile 1	23.0 kft	090	interrupt
090844		Profile 1	23.0 kft	279	resume
091541		Profile 1	27.0 kft	270	interrupt
091823		contrails	27.0 kft	063	
091841		no contr	27.0 kft	056	
091904		Profile 1	27.0 kft	056	resume
092951	093403	Run 1	27.0 kft	263	
093756	094846	Run 2	28.0 kft	078	
095125	100513	Run 3	29.1 - 29.0 kft	257	
100744	101243	Run 4.1	28.1 - 28.0 kft	085	
101545	102050	Run 4.2	28.0 kft	241	
102357	102925	Run 5.1	27.0 kft	101	
102543		contrail	27.0 kft	107	brief puffs as enteri ng cloud
103219	103822	Run 5.2	27.0 kft	265	
104120	104623	Run 6	25.0 kft	026	
104846	105523	Run 7	23.0 kft	241	
105916	110419	Run 8	19.0 kft	024	
111833	114902	Profile 2	18.0 - 35.0 kft	311	
112458		Profile 2	25.0 kft	321	interrupt
112814		Profile 2	25.0 kft	095	resume
114958		contrails	35.0 kft	013	
115128	120325	Run 9	35.1 - 35.0 kft	267	
120628	121544	Run 10	33.1 - 33.0 kft	090	
120718		contrails stopped	33.1 kft	088	
121035		contrails	33.0 kft	087	
121057		con stopped	33.0 kft	087	
121826	122934	Run 11	29.0 kft	261	
123213	124010	Run 12	27.1 - 27.0 kft	090	
124307	125100	Run 13	24.0 kft	265	
130408		asp closed	15.0 kft	251	
131840		Land	0.05 kft	233	at Inverness
132156		standstill	0.08 kft	093	57'32.45N, 4'03.73W
145858		T/O	0.06 kft	229	From Inverness
150418		asp open	11.4 kft	192	
155313		asp closed	22.0 kft	153	
160807		Land	0.22 kft	209	at Cranfield
161106		standstill	0.24 kft	310	52'04.36N, 0'37.50W

B122 Track 17-AUG-05

**Sortie Brief UTLS Cirrus 8 : Cirrus cloud microphysics and chemistry
Option 2 (Wave-cloud Cirrus)**

Flight Number B122

Date 17 July 2005

Mission Scientist: Keith Bower

Sortie Aims: To make measurements of the microphysics of cirrus clouds and their interaction with local aerosol and oxides of nitrogen. To investigate the effects of precipitation from the cloud on the vertical distribution of aerosol and oxidized nitrogen

Sortie Location: In layers of cirrus wave cloud over N.Scotland to the north of the Edinburgh/Glasgow region (Back-up region: in Ci to the NE of Scotland)

Sortie Summary: In orographic wave cloud cirrus. These will be used as a natural flow through reactor to study changes in the aerosol and trace gas composition, particularly focussing on oxides of nitrogen and nitrate. Initially a profile will be flown up wind of the cloud to assess the vertical structure of the atmosphere with respect to trace gases and aerosol properties. Straight and level runs will then be made along the wind, above within and below the wave clouds. These runs will cover the full horizontal extent of the cloud and will enable us to investigate both the microphysical evolution of the cloud and the influence of the cloud on the aerosol properties and the oxidised nitrogen species in the gas phase. These will be supplemented by runs upstream and downstream of the wave clouds perpendicular to the wind to investigate in detail the effects of the cloud processing on the aerosol properties and the oxidised nitrogen in the gas phase

Sortie Detail – assuming a refueling stop after the science flying.

- a. T+0 Take off and climb to FL200 for transit to operating area (a NO_x calibration should be undertaken where appropriate during transit – ie up to 20 minutes at FL150).
- b. T+70 Perform vertical profile through cirrus from below cloud base or –15°C level (whichever is higher) to aircraft ceiling, or to above cirrus top (whichever is lower).
- c. T+90 Descend to below cirrus and perform straight and level run along the mean wind direction 300 feet below cloud base for the length of the cloud. Do not sample if cloud temperature exceeds –15°C
- d. T+100 Turn through 180 degrees. Ascend to cloud base and perform straight and level run for length of cloud in cloud. Turn through 180 degrees ascend to middle of cloud and perform straight and level run for length of cloud.
- e. T+120 Return to upwind edge of the cloud and make straight and level run in inflow for the width of the cloud across wind.
- f. T+135 Travel to middle of the cloud and make straight and level run across wind for the width of the cloud
- g. T+146 Travel to downwind edge of the cloud and make straight and level run across wind for the width of the cloud
- h. T+160 repeat the sequence c-g as time permits .
- i. T+240 land and refuel
- j. T+330 takeoff for return transit (and include a SLR at FL150 for NO_x calibration)
- k. T+400 land Cranfield

Sortie Title UTLS Cirrus (Cirrus cloud microphysics & chemistry -Wave clouds Option 2)

Scientific Aims:

1. To measure the total number of Condensation Nuclei (CN), CCN, IN* and the size distribution of optically active particles in clean and polluted air in the UTLS region over the UK. Assessment of their spatial distribution and their likely source based on tracer measurements and air mass history.
2. To quantify the extent to which air mass history, and gas and particle loading can affect the microphysical properties of cirrus clouds in the UTLS region, in particular, the size distribution, phase and morphology of cloud particles.
3. To obtain estimates of HNO₃ loss to cirrus clouds and the subsequent effect on the aerosol population after the cloud has evaporated using case studies involving one or more wave clouds.
4. To make observations of the number, size distribution, phase and morphology of droplets and crystals in cirrus cloud and the number and size distribution of interstitial particles and correlate these with measurements of tracers that identify anthropogenic influence. Hence building on objective 3 to investigate the influence of cirrus on the distribution of aerosol and gases in the UTLS region as cloud and precipitation evaporate.
5. To make an assessment of the chemical composition of the particulate in the UTLS region as a function of their size, their spatial variability and the effect different sources have on their composition.
6. To use measurements of the masses of key components as a function of size of cirrus particle dry residues and interstitial particles to determine if there are distinct chemical differences between activated and unactivated particles.
7. To establish the partitioning of oxidised nitrogen between the gas and aerosol phases as a function of air mass history and source region

Weather conditions

Cirrus cloud associated with mountain waves preferably over the UK.

Key Measurements

Full suite of aerosol gas and microphysics equipment to be operated continuously. This includes aerosol and gas measurements in cloudy passes.

Video – the default recording setup should be forward and rear. Flight manager or Flight Scientists should monitor rearward video when at temperatures lower than -40C and note in logs the presence or absence of contrails. In any circumstance where a contrail appears to be on the margin of forming, a brief decrease in the engine power setting should be requested and any change in the contrail appearance noted.

Cloud Physics

- **FFSSP, 2DC, 2DP, PCASP, SID-1 and SID-2***. Normal monitoring to ensure correct operation. Operator should note particular features of interest eg. high concentrations, appearance of pristine ice crystal habits. (* If SID-2 computer suffers from regular crashes, then it may be operated so that data logging is only switched on during flight legs).
- **ADA/CPI** – as above
- **CCN** - alleviator should be filled whilst in clear air either below, between or upwind of the cloud layer(s) of interest. 1 sample per run, if possible.
- **J-W LWC and Nevzorov LWC/TWC**. Where run is only partially in cloud and starts in clear, these should be zeroed/calibrated and logged by Flight Manager.
- **TWC** – initial profile should avoid cloud, if possible, to achieve good calibration.

FWVS – Switch off the lamp when frost point rises above -15°C . Calibration should be performed following altitude changes.

WAS – On alongwind runs, 2 bottle samples per flight leg (one upwind of cloud and one downwind).

AMS to be operated on Rosemont inlet. Use CVI inlet on some in-cloud passes as called by mission scientist so require switching inlet. The inlet should be kept closed to avoid contamination whilst the GPU is operating prior to takeoff. It may be opened once the GPU has been removed. Similarly, intake should be closed before GPU is started post-flight.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CREW 8 -

Flight No **B.122**.....

Date **17/08/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
08:13:30	≡ 09:13:39			BS7 (KWS)	
08:55:43	BS7				Twee
09:02:32	BS7				T10
08:11:00	Cal.	FL140	333		NO ₂ Cal -
08:13:48		FL140	332	52.7N/1.1W	passed over Leicester - East Midlands ahead
					-2.53°C / -22.13°C 2m/s / 223° 549mb 25Skts
					AMS - Zero particle filter test - seeing particle - leak
09:27:56	BS7				NO ₂ Cal complete
					Rebooting WREACT - because of drop out
08:51:33	Trans	FL160	332	55.6/33W	-9.53 / -11.03°C 13m/s / 220°
09:53:00					RMTurn → to new satellite based based on Phil Brown's update
09:01:30	P1	FL180	68°		Start of P1
9:03:29	P1	FL		55.9/1.7W	-14.1 / -16.34°C 10/221° going W-E
					FL205 CB
			90		FL230 - CT 0
09:06:20	P1 int	FL230	90	55.9/1.3W	-19.38° / -20.21° 14m/s / 213° 409mb RMT
					small spheroidal + large egg Brossella
09:08:42	P1 rec	FL230	260	55.6/1.5W	concentration of ptbl - E-W
		FL250			-23.94 / -28.42° 14m/s / 230° (Cpt = 237°)
					Clouds - from Pennine - Ware? (cont - going - LW)
					Small spheroidal - C11 - Not on ADA
					FF550 - small N° dome
					CT 26300'
09:15:40	P1 int	FL270		55.9/2.4W	-28.4 / -29.76°C 344mb 12m/s / 201°

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CIRIUS 8

Flight No **B.122**.....

Date **17/08/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
					Some ice on Ford facing Cannon - after last dead
					Contracting too - 28.15 / -30.37 12m/s/215
09:18:50	P1 rc	FL270	56°	55.9/2.1W	OPI small IR ice - small rosettes - some rounded Some prolate
09:20:30	P1	FL280	56	56.0/1.9W	-31.25 / -31.52° 326 mb
09:21:40	P1	FL290	73	56.0/1.7W	-33.51 / 32.92° 311 mb
					OPI - lots small IR rosettes - plate aggregates
09:24:29	P1 int P1 end	FL300		56.1/1.2W	-36.66 / -36.89 301 mb 21m/s/230°
					OPI BR + large agg. rosettes now - edge of dead.
09:29:51	R1 st	FL270		56.0/1.7W	CON sample -28.59 / -29.25 17m/s/244 343 mb
09:32:00					CT 280-285
09:32:40					out of dead - not much
					2D - not many large particles may
					SIDI - high conc small particles - ice
09:34:08	R1 end				Will climb 1000' - and try to work along with
09:37:39		FL280			Chem Labs
09:37:55	R2 st	FL280	85°	55.9/1.5W	328 mb / -31.43°C
					OPI sm - large rosettes - occ spher/columnar
					OPI rosettes with plate aggs
					329 mb -30.91 / -33.60° 10m/s/240
09:41:40	R2	FL280			-30.91 / -34.0 7m/s/247° 328 mb
09:45:55	R2	FL280	84°	55.9/0.5W	SO ₂ base - descend west of this alt - switch off for now
09:47:10					CON finished

3 hrs -
with

3 hrs

Mission Scientist's Log

M.Sci KEVIN BOWER

CIRNUS 8

Flight No **B.122**.....

Date 17/08/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
09:46:43	R2 end	FL 280	turning	56.0/0.0	
09:51:20	R3	FL 290	256°	56.1/0.2W	-33.87/-36.65° 13 m/s / 265° 314 mb
09:54:38	R3	FL 290	256	56.0/0.7W	C. Chem coils down 553 lbs
					levelator / wave clouds ahead
					2 photographs - 220° wave clouds seen
09:50:ish	R3				CEN finished
10:03:50					straight thro top of cloud
10:05:12	R3 end	FL 290		55.9/2.3W	-33.9/-35.21 14 m/s / 214°
10:07:44	R4	FL 280	84°		
10:09:31	R4				In cloud again -32.7/-28
10:12:41	R4 end	FL 280	84°	55.8/1.3W	-30.90/-34.19°
10:14:43	R4.2 st	FL 280	364	55.9/1.5W	-30.92/-35.14 328 mb 16 m/s / 234° 339 lbs
10:17:45	R4.2				CEN finished - in cloud
10:19:35ish					Out of cloud
10:20:48	R4.2 end	FL 280		55.7/2.1W	R47 - need run 1000' lower
					CPI last passes :- v small proto particles inc size larger sometimes
10:23:54	RS.1 st	FL 270	103	55.8/2.0W	not along or across wind - can't do much about it
10:25:13					entering cloud 344 mb
10:25:47					entering cloud. 344 mb
10:29:22	RS.1 end	FL 270	100	55.7/1.2W	-28.35/-31.56°C 7 m/s / 247° 344 mb D47
10:32:17	RS.2 st	FL 270	265°		
10:34:10	RS.2	FL 270	261°	55.9/1.6W	Photo ahead -28.31/-21.55°C 344 mb
					2 Photo Ahead
10:30:21					Going into cloud

2 hrs + 10 mins left

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CIRRUS 8

Flight No **B B 122**

Date 17/05/05

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10:36:20	R5.2 end	FL 270	253	55.8/2.1W	end run - will go down
10:41:19	R6.1 st	FL 250			
10:42:21					in cloud. -24.52/-21.7 11m/s/224°
10:42:51					2D- just SIP probes seeing only small stuff 2D little CPI count.
10:46:21	R6.1 end	FL 250		56.1/1.4W	Will descend to FL 230
10:46:46	R7	FL 230	241	56.0/1.3W	Shunning CT's now (damn!)
					-19.7°C / -19.5° 13m/s / 235° 409mb
					Odd large column - pulsive plumes - eggs plate
					Now near CB
					Ice detected FFSSP - v low concs
					but wire not - seen it too.
					Out of cloud
10:55:03					Into cloud
10:55:22	R7 end			55.7/2.1	9/180° (-18.49 -18.53 416mb start of descent) (FL 223)
10:59:14	R8 st	FL 190	27	55.8/1.6W	-10.4 / -12.74°C 8m/s / 263° 484mb
11:02:30	R8	FL 190	24°	56.1/1.6W	just in CB's again
11:04:17	R6 end	FL 190	2°	55.6/1.5W	14m/s/248° -11.01/11.22° 490mb
		FL 183	310	57.1/2.8	-8.76 / -10.10 499mb 17 m/s / 230°
11:18:33	P2 start	FL 160	311	51.7/2.8W	Start climb - profile ascent
11:24:57	P2 int	FL 250	321	57.5/3.3W	-23.55 / -25.2° 32m/s / 229 376mb.
					In cloud - since transit at FL 180
11:28:11	P2 rec	FL 250	92°	57.4/3.2W	
11:29:55	P2	FL 263	80°	57.4.30W	Close to main CT

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci KEITH BOWER

CIRUS 8

Flight No **B**.....122.....

Date17/08/05.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
11:33:17	P2	28600	84	57.5/24	Near CT - or gap in cloud - break in cloud. New seed Herry CB
11:37:45	P2	31000	66	57.5/1.6W	286 mb 336 kts -35.95/-39.76 288 mb
11:39:50	P2	32000	85	57.6/1.2W	273 mb -41.49 / -41.41° 23 m/s / 226° CPI - eggs ~ 100-200µm - small brand plate 2D - 50/1hr 2DC 150-200µm (SODI - white)
11:45:00	P2	34600	87	57.7/0.4E	CPI 10-30µ < 100µm SIR, column 2D - 5/1 - much red
11:49:01	P2end	35000		57.7/0.6E	Conrad.
11:49:49					Conrad above - now creating our own
11:50:50	9	FL350	9	57.8/0.6E	-49.77 / -50.29 29 m/s / 269 236 mb
11:51:22	R9	FL350	266	57.8 / 0.5E	Wetlands - (NE Aberdeen) - -49.79 / -50.49°C
11:52:45	R9	FL350	263	57.8 / 0.3E	Core Chem Cal done - WAS stuck - CON stuck
11:56:20	R9				Seeing Odd Column - CPI
12:01:02	R9	FL350	265	9	2D - 15-20 hr \int 236 mb 33 m/s / 261°
12:02:28	R9	FL350	265	57.8 / 1.1W	SID2 - drop out. age \int -50.08 / -49.8°C
12:03:24	R9end	FL350	264	57.8 / 1.5W	CON finished - descending to FL330
12:06:27	R10st	FL330	90	57.7 / 1.4W	-44.53 / -44.59°C 26 m/s / 228° 261 mb CPI protine results - permiss. run: 1R Reginald + B Ross
12:14:46	R10			57.8 / 0.3E	Running out of CT now 261 mb
12:15:36	R10end	FL330	90	57.8 / 0.4E	-44.52 / -45.22° 19 m/s / 235° 261 mb
12:16:24					Underneath a Conrad. - probably ours
12:18:23	R11st	FL290	264	57.9 / 0.3E	23 m/s / 240° -33.4 / -36.65 314 mb

15

350
330
240
270

Mission Scientist's Log

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CIRrus 8

Flight No **B.122**.....

Date **17/08/05**.....

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GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
12:26:00	R11	FL210	265	57.9/0.6W	-33.63 / -35.52 25 m/s / 247° 314 mb
12:29:33	R11 end	FL290	264	57.9/1.2W	will descend to FL270 - CCN missed
12:32:02	R12	FL270	90	57.8/1.2W	343 mb, -28.22 / -29.12° 21 m/s / 241°
					Cloud is deeper at W end of run - nearer the front as per normal
12:37:44	R12	FL270	86	57.9/0.1W	Out of cloud bar here
					is a bit more cloud - then gaps again
12:39:50	R12	FL270	86		in CB again
12:40:09	R12 end	FL270	86	57.9/0.3W	will descend to FL240 for final leg
12:41:47				58.0/0.4E	below our control again
12:42:57	R13 ↓	FL240	264	58.0/0.1E	-21.06°C / -23.64° 19 m/s / 251° 392 mb 301 hPa
					started out of cloud - CCN sample - will run out cloud again shortly.
12:45:30 ↓	R13	FL240			CPI - chain aggregation - there are
12:47:37					see out to left - no cloud there - or here
12:48:20	R13	FL240			cloud on RHS, not on left 392 mb
					19 m/s / 245°
12:49:18	R13	FL240	261	58.0/0.5W	220 / 11 kts - Kinloss curled
12:50:59	R13 c	FL240	261	58.0/0.6	
		FL230	260		-19.67 / -21.57, 411 mb
		FL160			Out of CB
12:54:07	NO ₂ y	FL150	254	57.9/1.3	Cals -3.36° / -8.10° 16 m/s / 229°
					ADA - not seeing anything in current cloud
					(→ see oscillation?)
14:05:00	BS7 ICND				end of NO ₂ y Cal

301 hPa

14:12:23 7810'
5760'

CB -
Raining

CORE CHEMISTRY FLIGHT LOG FOR FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight Number : B122

Date : 17/8/05

Operator and contact info : Ruth Purvis (rupu@faam.ac.uk)

Problems with Instruments

CO	Problem with standard regulator
O₃	None
NO_x	Ozonator flow at high altitude therefore switched off between 11:50 and 12:45 GMT
SO₂	Switched off as no flow at high altitude
TDLAS	N/A
WAS	N/A

CO Calibrations

A full calibration lasts approx three minutes, it consists of a cal and a zero
Shorter (quick cal) are sometimes done at low level which is calibration only

<u>Time (GMT)</u>	<u>Level</u>	<u>Comments</u>
8:12	FL140	
unknown	FL140	
8:48	FL180	
9:26 – 9:27	FL300	Times are approx and may not be full calibration time
9:31 – 9:33	FL270	
9:38 – 9:41	FL280	
9:52 – 9:54	FL290	
10:23 – 10:26	FL270	
10:40 – 10:43	FL250	
10:48		Quick cal
11:07 – 11:10	FL180	
11:50 - 11:53	FL350	
12:06 – 12:08	FL330	
12:18 – 12:21	FL290	

CLLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B122

Date:05/09/05

Operator:MAP

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G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
09:05:30											Start Profile 1 (sid2 crash loss log)	
09:20:17	10	0.47	82		100	10	150	11			FL280	
09:21:26	3	0.08			10	20	275	11	50	200	11	FL290
09:24:25	1	0.08										End of Profile 1 @ FL300
09:29:53												Start Run 1 @ FL270
09:30:00	15	0.07	84		5				15			
09:32:00	10	1.12	86		3000	1	350	10				
09:34:00	6	0.07	87									
09:34:08												End of Run
09:37:58												Start Run 2 @ FL280
09:38:00	3	0.07							Noise			
09:40:00	200	0.72	88		100	15	300	10	10	200	11	
09:42:00	5	0.07										
09:44:00	5	0.08							10			
09:46:00	5	0.07							Noise			
09:48:45												End of Run
09:51:22												Start Run 3 @ FL290
09:52:00	4	0.07							Noise			
09:54:00	5	0.06				7	250	10	Noise			
09:56:00	4	0.20	89		20	6	200	10	500	200	11	
09:58:00	4	0.07							Noise			
10:00:00	4	0.07							Noise			
10:02:00	4	0.08							Noise			SID2 crash
10:04:00	3	0.16			1000	100	200	10	Noise			
10:05:14												End of Run
10:07:44												Start Run 4.1 @ FL280
10:08:00	5	0.08										
10:10:00	90	1.00			3000	25	250	10	Noise			Rearm 2 1
10:12:00	5	0.08										
10:12:46												End of Run
10:15:46												Start Run 4.2 @ FL280
10:16:00	5	0.07	90									
10:18:00	25	0.83	91		200	400	150	10	Noise			
10:20:00	7	0.08							Noise			

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B122

Date:05/09/05

Operator:MAP

Page 2 of 4

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
10:20:50											End of Run
10:24:00	8	0.08	91					Noise			Start Run 5.1 @ FL270
10:26:00	8	0.08						Noise			
10:28:00	11	0.08		1				Noise			
10:29:25											End of Run
10:32:20											Start Run 5.2 @ FL270
10:33:00	4	0.07									Rearm 2 64
10:35:00	6	0.07									
10:37:00	5	0.07									
10:38:23											End of Run
10:41:21											Start Run 6 @ FL250
10:42:00	8	0.07									
10:44:00	6	0.07		2	15	500	8	2900	400	11	
10:46:00	4	0.07									
10:46:24											End of Run
10:48:47											Start Run 7 @ FL230
10:49:00	4	0.08	100	2							
10:51:00	2	0.28	118	10	1	600	8	290	400	11	
10:53:00	12	0.08	124								
10:55:25											End of Run 7
10:59:16											Start Run 8 @ FL190
11:00:00	4	0.07	140								
11:02:00	10	0.14		1000	1	800	8	150	2000	8	
11:04:00	15	0.25	141	100	1	800	8	80	1600	8	
11:04:23											End of Run
11:18:34	450	0.05	288	100	100	800	8	5400	4000	8	Start Profile 2 from FL180
11:19:39	4	0.85	296	80	1	500	8	1000	800	8	FL190
11:20:35	85	0.88	297	100	50	750	8	7500	600	11	FL200
11:21:35	85	0.94	300	200	100	800	8	180000	600	11	FL210
11:22:23	100	0.99	307	125	100	600	8	160000	600	11	FL220
11:23:23	110	0.76	309	100	35	600	4	6900	600	11	FL230
11:24:36	20	0.76	312	60	50	600	4	4000	600	11	FL240
11:25:02	120	0.49	313	90	20	500	4	4700	600	11	FL250

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG

Flight No. B122

Date:05/09/05

Operator:MAP

Page 3 of 4

G.M.T.	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks	
	DRS Time	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size		Habit
11:29:19	25	0.85	321		40	20	500	4	6900	600	11	FL260
11:30:49	7	0.51	322		90	60	450	10	9100	400	11	FL270
11:31:58	25	0.66	323		90	50	250	10	800	200	11	FL280
11:33:39	25	0.89	324		10							FL290
11:35:17	11	0.40	325		90	125	175	10	110	200	11	FL300
11:37:38	4	0.13			100	80	175	10	110	200	11	FL310
11:39:47	5	0.08										FL320 SID2 Fail
11:44:59	3	0.13			10	1	100	11	Noise			FL340
11:49:05	5	0.09	326		10	1						End of Profile 2 @ FL350
11:51:25												Start Run 9 @ FL350
11:52:00	6	0.10			5	4			Noise			
11:54:00	6	0.11			5	3	50	11	Noise			
11:56:00	6	0.13			10	25	150	10	Noise			
11:58:00												SID2 Fail
12:03:35												End of Run
12:06:28												Start Run 10 @ FL330
12:07:00	70	0.65	327		30	20	175	10	Noise			
12:09:00	8	0.14			15	15	150	10	Noise			
12:11:00	5	0.10			5	3			Noise			SID2 fail
12:15:43												End of Run
12:18:27												Start Run 11 @ FL290
12:19:00	2	0.09	328									
12:21:00	5	0.10			2				Noise			
12:23:00	4	0.31			10	1			Noise			
12:25:00	50	0.47			20	10	300	10	Noise			
12:27:00												SID2 fail
12:29:39												End of Run
12:32:04												Start Run 12 @ FL270
12:33:00	3	0.41	335		80	25	200	10	3200	200	11	
12:35:00	60	0.71	336		60	30	350	10	5400	200	11	Rearm 2 64
12:37:00	35	0.66	337		10	5	350	10	25			
12:39:00	35	0.78			20	15	150	10	4700	200	11	
12:40:10												End of Run

CLLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B122

Date: 17/08/2005

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to PC B122_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data B122_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to the directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS	14/11/05	
3) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: B122 b) Path name: MFDDATA:B122_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: 0 if unknown e) End time: 240000 if unknown	29/11/05	MFD is faulty – will need to re-run – completed 29/11/05
4) RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: B122 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: Use the most recent calibration file. Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FFSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)	29/11/05	Note the calibration file used FFSSP_CAL23082005.TXT Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour Complete
5) In PVWAVE a) enter: !path=!path+',mrfb:[pms.proc]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! b) write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:B122_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:B122_mfdX','pmsdata:B122_m5procffssp',/auto 1st argument is output file from 5) 2nd argument is the MFD 3rd argument is the new FFSSP data file in M5 format c) exit	29/11/05	Note the correction applied to FFSSP time by /auto 20 sec subtracted from FFSSP time complete
6) MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B122_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:B122_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter updated MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default	29/11/05	

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG**Flight number:** B122**Date:** 17/08/2005

B) 2D PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Completed	Comments
1) Transfer B122.dat file from CD/DVD to PC		
2) Zip up file on PC (B122.zip)		
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS		
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B122.zip	14/11/05	
6) In PVWAVE		Note the number of bad block reads and/or final numbers of blocks read & written
i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]B122.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B122_seadas.dat iii) exit	14/11/05	Complete, no read errors
7) run MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE		
a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B122 c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] B122_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N	14/11/05	complete
8) 2D image display and printing		This section is optional
Quick look at image blocks if required In PVWAVE i) !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' ii) WAVE> IMAGEDISPLAY a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B122 c) IWC plot: N d) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP e) Start time: 0 if unknown f) End time: 240000 if unknown g) Time interval (sec): 0 for every image block nominal 5 sec Preparation of imagery for Core data product iii) WAVE> auto_image		

a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: B122 c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time 0 if unknown e) Enter end time 240000 if unknown f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks 10 iv) exit PVWAVE Creates files	090000 131500 10 PMSDATA:	FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_B122_2Dx_IMAGES.PS
ftp *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC		
Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter		
Output as pdf file (70 dpi resolution) and append name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	14/11/05	Complete. In O:\CloudPhysics Core data
9) run MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO		
a) Flight number: B122 b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: Hit enter d) Time correction: Time offset of the 2D data 0 e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:B122_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both 0 unless either probe known to be faulty h) Start time: 0 if unkown 090000 131500 (124958) 0.2 8 8 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown i) End time: 240000 if unknown j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown l) Coefficient choice: 2 2 m) Output root filename: PMSDATA:B122_PROC2D 29/11/05	0 090000 131500 (124958) 0.2 8 8 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown 2 2 29/11/05	As noted in operator log Data processing ended at 124958 when program crashed. This includes most of final flight leg so deemed OK. Data reprocessed with end time = 124958 Note the particle type MFD is faulty – need to re-run Completed 29/11/05
10) In PVWAVE		
i) enter: !PATH=!PATH+',MRFB:[PMS.PROC]' Note that the comma before "mrfb" is important! ii) WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:B122_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:B122_M5PROC2D' iii) exit	29/11/05	complete
11) MODIFY		
a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:B122_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:B122_mfdX c) New dataset: Enter modified MFD name d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default		Completed by first EXTRACTing a separate MFD starting at 083000. MODIFY could then be completed.

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	OFF	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
				1	2	3	4	5	
9:30 ⁴⁵		25135	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
			0.49					S	
			385					D	
			295					B	
			2451					R	
			836	836				P	Ditched
9:38:10		2518	0.49	0.69	1.1	1.041	2.01	S	
			850	449	1955	2012	3187	D	
			304	289	296	296	531	B	
			2459	2457	2458	2458	2453	R	
			826.7	827.4	826.8	827.1	827	P	
9:51:30		24.5	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
			0.49	0.72	1.04	1.42	2.01	S	
			386	1817	2606	2350	2513	D	
			276	289	295	329	570	B	
			2446	2448	2447	2446	2441	R	
			817.5	817.5	817.7	817.3	817.6	P	
10:07:50		25:24	0.49	0.72	1.08	1.41	2.03	S	
			439	1279	1415	1565	1799	D	
			270	285	291	297	385	B	
			2433	2427	2414	2398	2385	R	
			826.4	826.8	826.9	826.7	826.9	P	
10:28:00		24:32	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
			0.49	0.72	1.06	1.41	2.06	S	
			515	415	243	385	503	D	
			285	292	293	296	301	B	
			2368	2364	2351	2352	2348	R	
			835.9	835.7	836.2	836	836	P	
10:59:40		25:66	0.46	0.69	1.07	1.29	2.07	S	
			389	264	379	550	1171	D	
			259	246	246	240	280	B	
			2367	2371	2373	2378	2375	R	
			912.7	913	917.3	921.5	921.2	P	
									Dropped a 1000ft from 190-180
11:52:30		24:97	1.75	2.5	3.5	4.25	5.5		
			0.48	0.72	1.08	1.40	2.04	S	
			216	347	219	486	532	D	
			276	260	264	272	272	B	
			2363	2350	2366	2392	2387	R	
			750.8	750.9	750	751.6	751.6	P	
12:18:40		24:2	0.49	0.72	1.08	1.40	2.03	S	
			462	224	457	526	460	D	
			269	278	282	284	303	B	
			2462	2466	2470	2465	2471	R	
			817	817.3	817.3	817.2	817	P	

CCN LOG

ALLEVIATOR GMT	HEIGHT	TEMP INLET	STATIC					REMARKS
ON	OFF		1	2	3	4	5	
<i>124320</i>		<i>24.2</i>	<i>0.49</i>	<i>0.69</i>	<i>1.05</i>	<i>1.37</i>	<i>2.00</i>	S
			<i>1.75</i>	<i>2.5</i>	<i>3.5</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>5.5</i>	D
			<i>346</i>	<i>508</i>	<i>708</i>	<i>466</i>	<i>657</i>	B
			<i>270</i>	<i>274</i>	<i>280</i>	<i>280</i>	<i>300</i>	R
			<i>2480</i>	<i>2480</i>	<i>2480</i>	<i>2481</i>	<i>2489</i>	P
			<i>866.1</i>	<i>866.4</i>	<i>866.3</i>	<i>866.7</i>	<i>866</i>	
								S
								D
								B
								R
								P
			<i>1.75</i>	<i>2.5</i>	<i>3.5</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>5.5</i>	S
								D
								B
								R
								P
			<i>1.75</i>	<i>2.5</i>	<i>3.5</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>5.5</i>	S
								D
								B
								R
								P
			<i>1.75</i>	<i>2.5</i>	<i>3.5</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>5.5</i>	S
								D
								B
								R
								P
			<i>1.75</i>	<i>2.5</i>	<i>3.5</i>	<i>4.25</i>	<i>5.5</i>	S
								D
								B
								R
								P

Cont on p 1

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 17/08/05

FLIGHT: B122

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:	
Power ON	Ensure Inlet Closed	Inlet Valve	✓			
	Ensure Multiplier Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure Heater Off	Electronics box	✓			
	Ensure all Pumps Off	Pump Control box	✓			
	Turn on 230V Breaker	Power unit on a/c wall	✓			
	Turn on:	Electronics box power Diaphragm pump power Turbo pump power CPC Power, both Buttons	Power distribution box	✓ ✓ ✓ ✓		
	Open backing pump valve	Front facing side of rack.	✓			
	Turn on Alcatel... 100% speed	Pump Control Box, after #6	✓			
	Turbo pumps 2 and 3 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓	Monitor Pump Currents		
	Turbo pumps 4 and 5 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
	Turbo pump 6 ON... 100%	Pump Control Box	✓			
	Plug in CPC fill bottle	Rear of CPC	✓			
	Turn on heater	Electronics box	✓		Approx 2.8V, 0.9A	
Pre-Brief	Turn on Balzers Box	Power distribution box and Balzers box	✓			
	Turn on Copper	Electronics box	✓		Approx 125Hz	
	Turn on PC/Monitor	Power distribution box and PC	✓			
	Start AMS software	PC Desktop	✓			
	Turn autosaving off	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		NEGATIVE NUMBER	
	Reduce Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓			
	Set filament to 0.00mA, Scan range 0-300amu	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓			
	Turn Multiplier on	Electronics box	✓			
	Turn filament on @0.05mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓			

AMS PreFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 17/08/05

FLIGHT: B122

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Post Brief	Increase Multiplier voltage by 0.5kV	Parameter menu, Multiplier and chopper tab	✓		
	Close Grimm valve	Inlet valve	✓		
	CPC in low flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Check RF box, Tune if needed	Turn Tune Screw on RF Box for best hit	✓		
	Log CPC on AMS serial port 2	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Open AMS inlet	Inlet valve	✓		
	Increase filament to 2.5mA	MS mode, shift+B, click emission arrow	✓		
	Toggle chopper in MS mode	Press T within MS mode	✓		
	Check Airbeams and flows	Add m28 to m/z selection, Clean pin hole???	✓	F=1.9, AB approx 2.3MHz	1.96, 2.6
	Tune Balzers	Software	✓	Ensure no major changes	
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Gain approx 3e6	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	15, 16, 17, 30, 46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling, Calibrate, Save, Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1, a=0.41, 350nm	
	Remove CPC butanol from aircraft	Rear of CPC	✓		
	CPC in high flow	Shift+total on CPC display	✓		
	Reconnect inlet and GRIMM	Inlet	✓		
	Set CPC port=0 in AMS software	Parameter menu, Serial port tab	✓	LOG CPC IN LABVIEW	
	Set PC time with Horace	Desktop plus internet explorer	✓		
	Set mass range scan	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓	14, 16, 30, 43, 44, 46, 48, 57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software, m/z selection, left click on row	✓		
	Set DC marker 3 pos=6200	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓		(5680)
	Backup parameter file	C:\AMSVAMSCODE\AMSMMenu.prm	✓		
	Set save interval	Parameter menu, Averaging and saving tab	✓	0.5 minutes????	
Reconnect inlet, Close AMS valve	Inlet	✓			
Start CPC software	PC Desktop	✓			
General Alteration mode, Open Inlet	Software, Start after t/o	✓		09:00	

AMS Diagnostic Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 17/08/05 FLIGHT: B122

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time 0835

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	6.87	0.86	91.1	98
2	3.6	3.5	100	100
3	1.2	1	100	100
4	0.6	0.5	100	100
5	0.4	0.4	100	100
6	0.46	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.81	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	583	580
Heater B	73.3	75V
Multiplier	2.499	n/a
Pressure	0.067	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	1.63	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.26	2Mhz
Flow	1.30	2

Time 0940

no significant change 1040

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.58	0.86	88.8	98
2	2.30	3.5	100	100
3	1.18	1	100	100
4	0.60	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.80	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	583	580
Heater B	73.3	75V
Multiplier	2.500	n/a
Pressure	0.88	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	6	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	1.27	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.28	2Mhz
Flow	0.76	2

Time 1140

no significant change 1230

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel	0.52	0.86	89.2	98
2	2.15	3.5	100	100
3	1.13	1	100	100
4	0.57	0.5	100	100
5	0.41	0.4	100	100
6	0.43	0.46	100	100

	New	Typical
Heater V	2.80	2.5
Heater I	0.92	0.9
Heater T	73.3	580
Heater B	583	75V
Multiplier	2.499	n/a
Pressure	0.777	2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics	1	1A
I turbo	7	7A
I diaphragm	1.4	2A
MS AB	1.23	2.2Mhz
TOF AB	1.07	2Mhz
Flow	0.65	2

Time

Pump #	I(A)	I (typical)	Speed (%)	Speed typical
1/Alcatel		0.86		98
2		3.5		100
3		1		100
4		0.5		100
5		0.4		100
6		0.46		100

	New	Typical
Heater V		2.5
Heater I		0.9
Heater T		580
Heater B		75V
Multiplier		n/a
Pressure		2 Torr

	New	Typical
I electronics		1A
I turbo		7A
I diaphragm		2A
MS AB		2.2Mhz
TOF AB		2Mhz
Flow		2

AMS Calibration Log Sheet v2.00

DATE: 17/08/05 FLIGHT: B122

OPERATOR: G.C.

Tuning

pre-flight

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner	22	20	22
Def Outer	12	12	11
Heater Bias	-6.55	-6.36	-6.5
Focus	15.50	15.00	12.5
Extraction	240	224	220

TIME:	Old	New	Typical
Def Inner			22
Def Outer			11
Heater Bias			-6.5
Focus			12.5
Extraction			220

post-flight

Multiplier Cal

Might have to tweak filament current and multiplier voltage in order to set thresholds in calibration!!!!
This is done in the parameter menu..... Multiplier and Chopper Tab

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.500	n/a
KV Change	0.000	0.025kV
Gain	2.93	3.00E+06
G used Change	1.15	1

TIME:	New	Typical
KV	2.525	n/a
KV Change	0.025	0.025kV
Gain	2.83	3.00E+06
G used Change	0.96	1

Ionization Efficiency Cal

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.75	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	3.92	4
IPP NO3	407	400
IPP NH4	463	550
Airbeam MS	2.16	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	1.14	2.00E+06
Run Number	5994	n/a

TIME:	New	Typical
IE (NO3)	1.685 $\times 10^{-6}$	2.00E-06
RIE (NH4)	4.159	4
IPP NO3	392	400
IPP NH4	473	550
Airbeam MS	2.55 $\times 10^6$	2.20E+06
Airbeam TOF	2.86 $\times 10^5$	2.00E+06
Run Number	6470	n/a

Filter Run

TIME:	0814
Run number	5995

TIME:	1639
Run number	6471

leak! CPC & AMS recording
single particles, either tube/filter the prob.

AMS PostFlight Setup/Cal Sheet v2.00

DATE: 17/08/05

FLIGHT: 8122

OPERATOR: G.C.

Time:	Action:	Location:	Yes/No:	Notes	Comments:
Pre-land	Stop AMS,Grimm CPC logging	Software	✓		
	Close AMS inlet	Inlet	✓		
	Exit Labview		✓		
	Enable CPC in AMS software	Parameter Menu, Serial Ports tab	✓		
Post-land	Set CPC in Low Flow	Shift+totalizer on CPC display	✓		
	Open Inlet		✓		
	Turn off autosave (-ve number)	Parameter Menu,Averaging and saving tab	✓		
	Set mass range scan 0-300	Parameter menu, Mass Spectrometer tab	✓		
	Electron Multiplier Cal	Software, select suitable point manually	✓	Check gain at current V	
	Get tof masses for IE cal	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	15,16,17,30,46*	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓	wait	
	Mass Range Cal	MS mode, Click Mass Calibration	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	Run in MS-TOF alteration	Software	✓	Check tof windows	
	IE cal after 200 particles	Shift+M while sampling,Calibrate,Save,Exit	✓	SMPS s=4.1,a=0.41,350nm	
	Attach Zero filter to inlet		✓		
	Select tof masses to scan	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓	14,16,30,43,44,46,48,57	
	Set thresholds In tof mode	Left click "SP thresholds" in left border	✓		
	Add m28 to tof list	Software,mz selection,left click on row	✓		
	General alteration,10 mins	Software, F3 to NonAutoSave	✓	Check tof windows	
	Close inlet		✓		
Data	Copy AutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy NonAutoSaveData folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\NonAutoSaveDate	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy AMSLogFiles folder	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AMSLogFiles	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Copy CPC data	Source C:\UCPC\	✓		
		Dest C:\AMS\SAMSDData\Summer05\flight	✓		
	Backup directory to DVD/laptop		✓		
	Delete AutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER	
Delete NonAutoSaveData	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
Delete AMSLogFiles	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
Delete CPC data	Source C:\AMS\AMSDData\AutoSaveDate	✓	FILES ONLY, NOT FOLDER		
ShutDown	Turn off Multplier & Balzers	Electronics box	✓		
	Turn off all Turbos and PC	Pump Controller Box	✓		
	Shut Backing Valve	Back of rack	✓		
	Turn off heater,chopper,the rest	Electronics box, then power unit and Breakers	✓		

Flight Manager's Instrument Status Log

Flight No. **B122**

Date: 17/08/05

Instrument	Fitted	Operated	Instrument	Fitted	Operated
<u>Navigation</u>			<u>Cloud Physics</u>		
INU		Y	Probes		
XR5M GPS		Y	FFSSP		Y
Cruciform GPS	Y	N	PCASP		Y
Satcom C		Y	2D-P		Y
Satcom H		Y	2D-C		Y
<u>Thermometers</u>			Cloudscope	N	N
De-Iced Temp		Y	SID 1	Y	Y
Non De-Iced		Y	SID 2	Y	Y
Heimann	N		HVPS	N	
<u>Hygrometers</u>			CIP25	Y	N
G. Eastern		Y	CIP100	Y	N
J. Williams		Y			
Nevzorov		Y			
TWC		Y			
FWVS	Y	N	Racks:		
<u>Radiometers</u>			INC	N	N
Upper Clear	Y	Y	CCN / CNC		Y
“ Red	Y	Y	CVI	Y	Y
“ Silicon	Y	Y			
“ JO1D	Y	Y	<u>Aerosol</u>		
Lower Clear	Y	Y	PSAP	Y	N
“ Red	Y	Y	Nephelometer	N	
“ Silicon	Y	Y	Filters	Y	Y
“ JO1D	N		AMS	Y	Y
<u>Large Radiometers</u>					
TAFTS	N				
MARSS	N				
DEIMOS	N		<u>Others:</u>		
ARIES	N		NIR TDLAS	Y	N
SWS	N		2BT O3	Y	N
<u>Chemistry</u>			VACC	Y	N
Ozone	Y	Y	PEROXIDE	Y	N
SO2	Y	Y	Formaldehyde	Y	N
NOX	Y	Y	ADA	Y	N
CO	Y	Y	CPI	Y	N
ORAC	Y	N	NOxy	Y	Y
PAN	Y	N	PTRMS	Y	Y
PERCA	N	N	Bag Sampling	Y	N
WAS	Y	Y			

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B122

Date: 17/08/05

Instruments

1. Core Chemistry CO calibration regulator diaphragm leak. Cylinder left off unless in use – needs fixing.
2. DFC intermittently reporting “Motion Alarm Area 1” on screen.
3. Data dropping out on display. In case this was also in horace, data logging system was restarted after horace was shut down. Drop-outs continued. Raw DRS readings seemingly unaffected. Eventually fixed problem by exchanging the optical disk – bad disk causing write errors and interrupting the lower-order processing.
4. Core Chem NOx / NO data unavailable from 11:50 to 12:45 owing to low flow at high altitude.

Aircraft

1. Preflight bin missing – eventually located in passenger search area
2. Flight Manager Comms box unable to transmit. Avalon fixed preflight by pressing and depressing ‘voice’ button. Problem recurred during flight (while speaking), switched to training and back to mission to clear problem.
3. Seemingly a problem with PTRMS and Core Chem comms boxes before takeoff. FM couldn’t hear them and they couldn’t hear him, fiddling with boxes seemed to cure the problem.

Satcom H Calls -

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following logs are not available for flight B122:

Log	Reason
De-brief	Sortie De-brief yet to be created by Keith Bower
CVI	No log is ever taken for CVI
NOxy	No log is ever taken for NOxy
PTrMS	No log is ever taken for PTrMS
CPI	Log only of interest to instrument operator so no copy left with FAAM

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

1 x Forward Facing Cameras
1 x Rearward Facing Cameras

8mm video recordings from this flight reside with :
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :
8mm video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :
Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with FAAM (at 31 Oct 2005) :

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New plot, same times

Flight B122 08:43:21

Heading 347 deg Speed 323 knots Height 18.0kft Press 505mb

Lat 54.8N Long 2.8W Wind 7 ms-1/ 231 deg

Temp -9.85C Dewpoint -27.57C

From 08:09:24 to now

Current values			
— TIME FROM MIDNIGHT	31401	secs	☉ All
— OZONE MIXING RATIO	71.48	ppb	☾
— CO MIXING RATIO	87.11	ppb	☽